

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF LAVENDER ESSENTIAL OIL GROWING IN TAJIKISTAN

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Abstract. Essential oils are a good source of several bioactive compounds with antioxidative and antimicrobial properties. In this work, we obtained the EO of lavender grown in an experimental plot in Dushanbe. The chemical composition of the oil, which contains 64 components, was studied using GC-MS. This oil contains mainly linalol (33.27%) and linalyl acetate (21.01%); the content of other significant essential oils is terpine-4-ol (6.89%); eucalyptol (1.88%), trans- β -ocene (2.24%); lavandulol (4.91%); caryophyllene (1.81%). The resulting lavender essential oil exhibits antioxidant activity when diluted 1:10 and 1:50 times.

Keywords: essential oil, chemical composition, linalool, antioxidant activity.

EO found in many different plants, especially the aromatic plants, vary in odor and flavor, which are governed by the types and number of constituents present in oils. Additionally, the amount of essential oil from different plants is different and this determines the price of essential oil. Apart from aromatic compounds, indigenous pigments contribute to varying colors of essential oil. This can affect the applications as the ingredient in some particular foods. Essential oils have been known to possess antioxidant and antimicrobial activities, thereby serving as natural additives in foods and food products. Almost any part of a plant may be the source of the oil, which could be extracted and fully exploited for food applications or others. Modern technologies have been continuously developed to conquer the limitation of conventional methods, and to enhance the extraction efficacy [1].

In pharmaceutical industries, medicines in the form of capsules, syrups, ointments, creams, and sprays contain some compositions of essential oils and their production numbers are constantly growing. Thus, the applications of essential oils in numerous fields: food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries are still being investigated in order to formulate and produce more efficient essential oil-based products [2].

There are more than 200 components present in pure essential oils which are normally mixtures of terpenes, and phenylpropanoid derivatives, in which the chemical and structural differences between compounds are minimal. The constituents of essential oils may be broadly classified as volatile and non-volatile fractions. The overall chemical composition of the aromatic oil volatile fraction includes mono- and sesquiterpene components, and several oxygenated derivatives along with alcohols, aliphatic aldehydes, and esters. On the other hand, 1-10 wt% of isolated essential oil comprises carotenoids, fatty acids, flavonoids and waxes which are classified as non-volatile residues [3]

This work aims to obtain lavender essential oil and study EO chemical composition.

Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*), grown at the experimental site of the Institute of Botany, Physiology, and Plant Genetics of the National Academy of Sciences of Tajikistan, was collected in early June in the morning. Lavender stems were cut 10-15 cm long and dried under natural conditions in the air at room temperature in the shade. The yield of finished raw materials during drying was 46.61%.

Lavender essential oil (EO) was obtained by the hydrodistillation method described in [4], with a yield of 0.86% of the total mass of the dry product. EOs had the following physical characteristics: the density of lavender EOs is 0.873 g/ml, and the refractive index of light at 20°C is 1.459.

Composition analyses were performed on an Agilent 7890B-5977A GC-MS. According to the results of GC-MS, a sample of lavender essential oils growing at the Institute of Botany, Physiology, and Plant Genetics of NAST contains 64 components. The main components of this EO were linalol and linalyl acetate, with percentages of 33.27% and 21.01%, respectively. Other significant components of lavender essential oil were terpene-4-ol (6.89%), eucalyptol (1.88%), trans- β -science (2.24%), Lavandula (4.91%), borneol (2.23%), etc.

The antioxidant activities of lavender oil have been studied. Table 1 shows the results of the analysis. According to the data obtained, it is clear that EO shows maximum antioxidant properties when diluted to 1:10 times. With further dilution up to 1:100, the antioxidant activity of the oil decreases.

Table 1. Antioxidant analysis data for EO lavender plot - Institute of Botany, Physiology, and Plant Genetics of NAST.

Sample	Dilution	Abs sample (517 nm)	Abs control (517 nm)	AOA, %
EO	1:10	0.0686	0.1195	42.60
	1:50	0.0836	0.1195	30.04
	1:100	0.1096	0.1195	8.28
	1:200	0.1156	0.1195	3.30

Thus, this work presents the results of the chemical composition and antioxidant activity of lavender essential oil growing in Tajikistan. This oil contains linalool (33.27%) and linalyl acetate (21.01%); the content of other significant essential oils is terpene-4-ol (6.89%), eucalyptol (1.88%), trans- β -one (2.24%); Lavandula (4.91%); caryophyllene (1.81%). The resulting lavender essential oil exhibits antioxidant activity when diluted 1:10 and 1:50 times.

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